

Sustainable Plant-Based Protein Powder Formulation and Its In Vitro Nutraceutical Evaluation

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ABSTRACT

Proteins are essential components of the human diet. Dietary proteins can be derived from animal or plant sources. Animal-based foods such as meat and dairy products are very rich in protein content. Currently, there is an increasing demand for protein-rich food in the global market. The people are becoming more aware of the constructive role of proteins in human wellbeing. But the animal protein is considered less environmentally sustainable. Therefore, plant-based food can be a promising approach due to multiple aspects such as maintaining environmental stability, ethical reasons, food affordability, greater food safety, fulfilling higher consumer demand, and combating protein-energy malnutrition. The protein content of plant-based sources, that is, cereals, legumes, nuts, and seeds, is comparatively higher than milk and almost similar to meat. This study was focused on the formulation of plant-based protein powder using pulses such as Soyabean, Rajma, Red-chana, Masur and their comprehensive evaluation for nutritional properties. The pulses selected in this work are comparatively less consumed, even though having significant protein content. So the daily diet can be enriched with a food supplement with high protein content. The formulated protein powder was analysed for its protein, iron, folic acid, vitamin C and carbohydrate content, using simple, specific in vitro assays. All nutraceutical properties were analysed for individual samples as well as the formulated product by simple in vitro assays. The plant-based formulated protein blend was showing higher nutritional content compared to the individual sample tested.

Keywords: Plant-based, nutritional properties, protein, Vitamin C, Iron, carbohydrate, folic acid

INTRODUCTION

Proteins are one of the essential nutritional components of the human diet. With the increasing world population, there is a significant increase in demand for food, particularly protein-rich food and feed. This demand for protein-rich food in the global market is also due to increasing consumer awareness about the constructive role of protein in human well-being. (Sheetal et al. 2024) Proteins in the human diet vary in chemical, biological, functional, and nutritional characteristics

depending on their source, molecular makeup, and structures. Dietary proteins could be derived from animals and plants, and there are important differences in the type of protein derived from them. The differences include molecular structure, amino acid profile, digestibility, and technical functionality in food, ability to bind water etc. These basic differences greatly affect their bioavailability from a human nutrition point of view. Animal-based foods, that is, meat and dairy products, have been consumed for protein uptake, so globally there is a high demand for them. But the animal protein is considered less environmentally sustainable. (Sapna et al. 2021).

Nowadays, there is an increase in awareness about environmental pollution, animal cruelty and the adverse effects of animal-based food products on consumers' health. Therefore, a replacement of animal-based protein food with the plant-based one can be preferred due to many reasons, like maintaining environmental stability, ethical reasons, food affordability, greater food safety, higher consumer demand fulfilment, and combating protein-energy malnutrition. Therefore, plant-based proteins are becoming popular nowadays, and this trend may continue in the upcoming years. Plant proteins are a good source of many essential amino acids, vital macronutrients, and are sufficient to achieve complete protein nutrition. Plant-based proteins are considered vegan food, provide an ample number of amino acids, are directly absorbed by the body, and help in treating various diseases. Moreover, the proteins derived from plant-based foods are rich in fibre, polyunsaturated fatty acids, oligosaccharides, and carbohydrates.

Protein intake in the routine human diet comes from whole foods. The protein content of plant-based sources, that is, cereals (6%–15%), legumes (20%–38%), pseudocereals (11%–23%), nuts (18%–38%) and seeds (9%–30%) is comparatively higher than milk (3%–5%), whereas approximately similar to meat (23%). The heightened consumer awareness has globally influenced the production, distribution, sale and consumption of plant-based foods. (Christabel et al. 2023) Therefore, considering increased interest in plant-based protein diets, the present work was primarily focused on the formulation of a plant-based protein blend. The raw materials are loaded with abundant plant proteins and can be obtained after extraction. The Extraction methods are mainly of two categories: conventional extraction methods and novel

extraction techniques. Conventional methods are restricted by long extraction time, low extraction selectivity, expensive high-purity solvents, large amounts of solvent evaporation, and degradation of thermolabile proteins (Selva-Muthukumaran & Shi, 2017). With the increasing global population, there is a continuous increase in demand for the supply of protein. Hence, the need to search for new sources. The extraction of an adequate amount of animal protein is quite hard and expensive. Therefore, an alternative for improving the nutritional status of humans is mainly derived from plant proteins. Hence, evaluation of the nutritional quality of proteins from different plant species is now focused. Different sources of plant-based protein include legumes like Red chana (*Cicer arietinum*), Rajma (*Phaseolus vulgaris*), Soyabean (*Glycine max*), Masur (*Lens culinaris*), etc. Soyabean as an excellent source of plant-based protein, containing all nine essential amino acids, making it a complete protein source. Soya provides a valuable source of protein for those following vegetarian or vegan diets, as it provides a complete protein source without animal products. Red chana, also known as chickpeas, is a great source of plant-based protein and carbohydrates, fibre and certain minerals like iron and phosphorus. The high fibre content and protein contribute to fullness, potentially aiding in weight management. Rajma is a good source of protein, essential for muscle growth, repair and overall body function. Rajma is also a good source of iron, which supports heart health, blood pressure and red blood cell production. Masur (Red lentils), rich in protein, can be used in different dishes, making it a versatile, nutritious supplement in the diet. Masur can also help keep skin moisturised and healthy due to the presence of Vitamin B.

The present work focuses on formulating the sustainable plant-based protein powder using the extracted protein from Red chana, Soybean, Rajma, and Masur. The formulated protein blend was further analysed for its various nutritional properties such as net protein, vitamin C, folic acid, and Iron content.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

1. Sample Preparation

Dry seeds of four legumes, Soyabean, Rajma, Red-chana, and Masur, collected from the local market, were dehulled and milled. The shells were removed and ground to make fine powder. All four separate

legume powders were used for crude protein content estimation by the Folin-Lowrey method.

2. Protein isolation from dry legume powders by alkaline Extraction method (Bello et al 2023)

Dehulling and milling of all pulses were carried. The shells were removed and ground to make fine powder. All four separate legume powders were used for protein isolation by Solvent extraction using Chloroform. The isolated protein was purified by salt precipitation using ammonium sulfate

3. Estimation of protein by Bradford assay.

The Bradford assay using Coomassie Brilliant blue reagent is based on the principle that the dye Coomassie Brilliant blue binds to protein and changes its adsorption.

4. Estimation of vitamin C using titration method.

Ascorbic acid was used as a standard for Vitamin C estimation.

5. Estimation of iron.

A commercially available Iron tablet was used for the preparation of an iron solution. Using this as a standard, the iron content in the formulated protein sample was spectrophotometrically estimated at 562 nm.

6. Estimation of folic acid.

Folic acid content was estimated using Sodium nitroprusside and ammonia reagent. Commercially available, a Folic acid tablet of known concentration was used as a standard.

7. Estimation of carbohydrate.

The carbohydrate content of the formulated protein sample was estimated by the Anthrone assay.

RESULTS

Sample Preparation

Dry seeds of four legumes, Soyabean, Rajma, Red-chana, and Masur, were collected from the local market.

Protein isolation from dry legume powders by alkaline Extraction method

All the dry powders of legumes were used for crude protein content estimation by the Folin-Lowrey method.

The crude protein content of the individual legume sample was calculated using the standard graph of protein estimation by the Folin-Lowrey method. The Soy powder showed maximum protein concentration, thus rich in protein content as compared to the other three legumes used.

Fig. 1: Fine powder of all four legumes

Graph 1: Protein estimation of individual legume samples.

Protein isolation from dry legume powders by alkaline Extraction method

Respective legume powders and an equal proportion of all four legume powders were further subjected to Protein Isolation by the alkaline extraction method. The present method was found to be an efficient one, as a significant amount of protein was precipitated out. The amount of protein precipitated was estimated by the Bradford method using Coomassie Brilliant blue reagent. From the in vitro protein estimation by Bradford Assay, comparative protein content for isolated protein samples of individual legumes and the

formulated one, it was clear that the formulated sample show maximum of 20.91 mg/ml. This formulated protein sample was air-dried and then stored at room temperature. 1mg/ml aqueous suspension of the same was used further for analysis of nutraceutical properties.

Estimation of vitamin C using titration method.

From the mean burette reading for vitamin C estimation by titration method, it was revealed that

the formulated protein sample was also showing significant vitamin C content.

Estimation of iron.

A standard commercially available iron tablet was used as a control for the estimation of the Iron content in the formulated protein sample. Along with significant protein content, the sample was showing a considerable amount of iron, 6.14 mg/ml.

Graph 2: Estimation of the concentration of extracted protein of individual legume samples and formulated one

Fig2:- Bradford Assay

Fig 3 :- Vitamin C Estimation

Graph 3: Estimation of Iron Content

Fig. 4 Estimation of Iron

Graph 4: Estimation of Folic Acid

Estimation of Folic Acid

A standard commercially available Folic acid tablet was used as a control for folic acid estimation of the protein sample.

Estimation of carbohydrate.

Total carbohydrate content of the protein sample was estimated using the standard graph of Carbohydrate estimation using the anthrone

DISCUSSION

People are currently facing protein and mineral deficiency in their diet throughout the world, particularly in developing countries. The root cause is lower consumption of pulses and cereals in their diets and other foods that are rich in zinc, iron, calcium, and magnesium. (Sapna et al.2022) Dietary protein plays a critical role in several physiological processes in the body. For the overall healthy living of individuals, an appropriate intake of protein is essential. The human diet includes traditional sources of protein, both plant-based and animal-based. Proteins, in general, are formulated in powder form as it offers ease of transportation and increased shelf-life by reducing

their water activity. Recently, there has been an increasing interest in proteins of plant origin rather than animal origin because of their environmental sustainability, animal welfare, ethical reasons, animal protein allergies, and an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases. Therefore, plant protein extraction, enrichment, purification, functionalization, and improving powder properties are of great significance nowadays. In the present study, a plant-based protein powder was formulated, extracted, and evaluated for its nutraceutical properties, bioactivity, and nutritional quality. The results indicated that the formulated protein powder is rich in iron and folic acid, which are essential for maintaining healthy red blood cells and preventing anaemia. The vitamin C in the protein may facilitate amino acids absorption. The carbohydrate estimation revealed a moderate level of carbohydrates, which can provide sustained energy release.

CONCLUSION

The plant-based protein powder formulated through this study exhibits excellent protein content and other nutraceutical properties. The research suggests that

this protein powder can be a valuable dietary supplement for individuals of all ages, including children, seeking to manage oxidative stress, blood sugar levels, and maintain overall health. Furthermore, the plant-based protein powder offers a sustainable and environmentally-friendly alternative to traditional animal-based protein powders.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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